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International Network Center for Fundamental and Applied Research

«Approved»

Director

Doctor of historical sciences

A.A. Cherkasov

January 9, 2019

REPORT of scientific activities

for 2018

Washington, 2018

Main provisions on the presentation of the report

- 1.1. The report on the scientific activity is represented by the laboratories included in the structure of the center.
- 1.2. The report includes indicators on the main activities provided by the Charter of the organization.
- 1.3. Reports on research activities of laboratories are considered at their meetings and approved by the director of the center.
- 1.4. Summary reports of the laboratories are prepared by 20 December 2018.

The effectiveness of research work in 2018

1.1. Thesis Defense

№	Full name of the dissertator (organization, division, position)	The theme of the thesis	Declared academic degree, specialty (code, name)	Scientific head (consultant) – academic degree, academic title, surname and initials)	City, university dissertation board (board code), date of defense	Series, number of diploma of doctor (candidate) of sciences, date of approval
1	Polyakova L.G.	The Black sea province during the First world war (on the materials of the periodical press)	Candidate of Historical Sciences (07.00.02 – National history)	Doctor of historical sciences, associate professor A.A. Cherkasov	Stavropol, North Caucasus Federal University, Board code D 212.245.12 21.12.2018	-

1.2. Monographs

№	Title	Author (s)	Publisher, city	The year of publishing	Number of pages	Circulation
1	-	-	-	-	-	-

1.3. Articles in scientific journals (Scopus and WoS)

№	Title of the article in its original language	The authors (full name) (center employees are highlighted in bold)	Journal title	Country	Scopus	Web of Science	Output data
1	Concerning the Iranian Influence on the Georgian Military Organization (According to the example of «Morighe Lashkari» or «Morighe» – second half of XVIII c.)	N. Ter-Oganov	Bylye Gody	Slovakia	X	X	2018. 47(1): 53-59.
2	The Circassian Aristocracy in the late XVIII – the first half of XIX centuries: the Social Structure of Society	A.A. Cherkasov , M. Smigel, S. Bratanovskii, A. Valleau	Bylye Gody	Slovakia	X	X	2018. 47(1): 88-96.
3	The Plague in the Caucasus in 1801–1815 years: Part I	I.A. Ermachkov , L.A. Koroleva, N.V. Svechnikova, J. Gut	Bylye Gody	Slovakia	X	X	2018. 47(1): 120-129.

4	The Exchange of Prisoners as a New Form of the Russian-Circassian Dialogue at the beginning of the 19th Century: Part II	G. Rajović, D.O. Ezhevski, A.G. Vazerova, M. Trailovic	Bylye Gody	Slovakia	X	X	2018. 47(1): 153-160.
5	The Struggle for Literacy in the Russian Troops in the late 1850s – early 1860s	O.V. Natolochnaya, B.A. Bulgarova, M.A. Bragina	Bylye Gody	Slovakia	X	X	2018. 47(1): 225-231.
6	Muhajirun – the Reasons and Scales of Resettlement of Mountaineers of the Northwest Caucasus	S.J. Suschiy, A.M. Mamadaliev, S.F. Artemova	Bylye Gody	Slovakia	X	X	2018. 47(1): 292-301.
7	Slave Trade and Slavery in the Central Asian Outskirts of the Russian Empire (XVIII–XIX centuries)	Y.A. Lysenko	Bylye Gody	Slovakia	X	X	2018. 47(1): 172-182.
8	Development of Foreign Language Lexical Competence on the Basis of a Learner's Terminological Thesaurus and Dictionary	G.R. Chainikova, A.V. Zatonskiy, N.W. Mitiukov, H.L. Busygina	European Journal of Contemporary Education	Slovakia	X	X	2018, 7(1): 51-59.
9	School and University in Soviet Cinema of "Perestroika" (1986–1991)	A. Fedorov, A. Levitskaya, O. Gorbatkova, A. Mamadaliev	European Journal of Contemporary Education	Slovakia	X	X	2018, 7(1): 82-96.
10	Teaching Singing in the Russian Empire Educational Institutions: Importance and Results	V.S. Molchanova, S.F. Artemova, L.L. Balaniuk	European Journal of Contemporary Education	Slovakia	X	X	2018, 7(1): 220-225.
11	Public Education in the Russian Empire at the end of the 19th century	N.A. Shevchenko, I.A. Kucherkov, D.A. Shirev, N.V. Miku	European Journal of Contemporary Education	Slovakia	X	X	2018, 7(1): 226-231.
12	The development of the principles of writing of the official history of the Cossacks in the ministry of war	A.Yu. Peretyatko	Vestnik of Saint Petersburg University. History	Russian Federation	X	X	2018, 63(2): 546-571.
13	The Black Sea Province in the First World War: A Historiographical Review	L.G. Polyakova, L.L. Balanyuk	Bylye Gody	Slovakia	X	X	2018. 48(2): 838-849.
14	The Discussion between Central and Regional Authorities on the Topic of the Affiliation of Muslim Schools in Turkestan (the late half of the 19th – the beginning of the 20th centuries)	Y.A. Lysenko	Bylye Gody	Slovakia	X	X	2018. 48(2): 759-767

15	Formation of Ideas about the Siberian Region Pedagogical Press of the late XIX – early XX centuries (on the example of the journal "Russian School")	I.V. Pivovarova, Y.V. Putilina, Y.V. Zubareva, A.M. Mamadaliyev	Bylye Gody	Slovakia	X	X	2018. 48(2): 750-758.
16	Migration Problems in Survey of Liberal Press the second half of XIX – early XX centuries	V.N. Cherepanova, I.A. Filippova, V.S. Molchanova	Bylye Gody	Slovakia	X	X	2018. 48(2): 719-727.
17	Seamen in the Gasp-Tekinskoy Expedition	Y.F. Katorin, A.P. Nyrkov, V.B. Karataev	Bylye Gody	Slovakia	X	X	2018. 48(2): 628-638.
18	Letters as a Source of Propaganda during the Kakheti Uprising of 1812	G. Rajović, D.O. Ezhevski, A.G. Vazerova, M. Trailovic	Bylye Gody	Slovakia	X	X	2018. 48(2): 570-575.
19	The Plague in the Caucasus in 1801–1815 years: Part II	I.A. Ermachkov, L.A. Koroleva, N.V. Svechnikova, J. Gut	Bylye Gody	Slovakia	X	X	2018. 48(2): 558-569.
20	Eastern Georgia and the Protectorate of the Russian Empire (1783-1801): Terms, Features and Outcomes of Political Interaction	A.T. Urushadze, A.A. Cherkasov, A. Valleau	Bylye Gody	Slovakia	X	X	2018. 48(2): 538-548.
21	Students' Humanitarian Science Club Activity in 2006–2012	I.A. Ermachkov, A.I. Ekimov, A.G. Vazerova	European Journal of Contemporary Education	Slovakia	X	X	2018, 7(2): 286-290.
22	Psychometric Properties of the Scale of Mato and Muñoz-Vázquez in Medical Undergraduate Students Sample	A. García-Santillán, R. Viridiana García-Cabrera, V.S. Molchanova, V. García-Cabrera	European Journal of Contemporary Education	Slovakia	X	X	2018, 7(2): 332-343.
23	Development of Communicative Tolerance among Teachers of Primary and Senior Level of the General Education School	Y.P. Povarenkov, N.A. Baranova, A.D. Sidorova, N.W. Mitiukov	European Journal of Contemporary Education	Slovakia	X	X	2018, 7(2): 372-378.
24	The System of Teaching Literacy in Company Schools of the Russian Army: the 1850–1860s Experience	O.V. Natolochnaya, A.A. Korolev, O.V. Ustinova, T.E. Zulfugarzade	European Journal of Contemporary Education	Slovakia	X	X	2018, 7(2): 413-419.
25	Regional Problems of Public Schools in the Russian Empire in 1869–1878 (using an example of the Vyatka Province)	T.A. Magsumov, S.F. Artemova, L.L. Balanyuk	European Journal of Contemporary Education	Slovakia	X	X	2018, 7(2): 420-427.

26	The Class List of Secondary Educational Institutions' Pupils in Siberia at a boundary of the 19th-20th centuries	V.N. Rodina, O.V. Kirilova, K.V. Taran	European Journal of Contemporary Education	Slovakia	X	X	2018, 7(2): 428-435.
27	Sacred pagan temples in the caucasus region: Characteristic features	A. Cherkasov , L. Koroleva, S. Bratanovskii, M. Smigel	Muzeologia a Kulturne Dedicstvo	Slovakia	X	X	2018, 6(2): 59-69.
28	Witchcraft, sorcery and hand wringing in the life of siberian peasants: On the materials of historical sources of the nineteenth century	Y.V. Putilina, O. Ustinova, N. Shevchenko	Muzeologia a Kulturne Dedicstvo	Slovakia	X	X	2018, 6(2): 71-81.
29	The Policy of the Tsarist Authorities to Involve Mingrelia in the Political and Legal Space of the Russian Empire (1774–1857)	V.G. Ivantsov, Yu.N. Makarov, L.G. Zimovets, N.A. Shevchenko	Bylye Gody	Slovakia	X	X	2018. 49(3): 1019-1027.
30	General Ermolov and His Role in the Evolution of Public Health Service in the Caucasus	I.A. Ermachkov , L.A. Koroleva, N.V. Svechnikova, J. Gut	Bylye Gody	Slovakia	X	X	2018. 49(3): 1037-1045.
31	Features of Wedding Traditions and Rituals in the Territory Siberian Region in the XIX – Early XX Centuries	Yu.V. Putilina, O.V. Ustinova, O.V. Natolochnaya	Bylye Gody	Slovakia	X	X	2018. 49(3): 1111-1118.
32	The Plague in the Caucasus, 1835–1839: Features of Detection and Counteraction	G. Rajović , D.O. Ezhevski, A.G. Vazerova, M. Trailovic	Bylye Gody	Slovakia	X	X	2018. 49(3): 1119-1124.
33	From the History of the Development of Controlled Aerostats (Airships) in the XIX – early XX centuries	V.B. Karataev , P.Yu. Grosheva, L.V. Shkvarya	Bylye Gody	Slovakia	X	X	2018. 49(3): 1159-1165.
34	"The Case of the Loss of the Russian Peasant Settlers in the Steppe Region of Religious and Moral and National Character": the Position of the Russian Orthodox Church (end of XIX – beginning of XX centuries)	Yu.A. Lysenko	Bylye Gody	Slovakia	X	X	2018. 49(3): 166-1174.
35	Reconstruction of the Order's Numbers of the Votkinsk Plant's Shipbuilding Workshop on 1865-1902	N.W. Mitiukov , A.N. Loshkarev, D.V. Matveev	Bylye Gody	Slovakia	X	X	2018. 49(3): 1203-1215.

36	Coverage of the Siberian Theme on the Pages of Historical Magazines of the second half of the XIX – early XX centuries (on the example of the magazine " Russian Antiquity»)	I.V. Pivovarova, Yu.V. Putilina, Yu.V. Zubareva, A.M. Mamadaliyev	Bylye Gody	Slovakia	X	X	2018. 49(3): 1216-1223.
37	"We Have Not Done Anything": The First Stage of Work on the Official History of the Don Cossacks (1902-1908)	A.Y. Peretyatko	Bylye Gody	Slovakia	X	X	2018. 49(3): 1258-1269.
38	Steamers of the Izhevsk's Plants on the 1910-s	N.W. Mitiukov, S.L. Bautina, S.I. Adinyaev	Bylye Gody	Slovakia	X	X	2018. 49(3): 1307-1320.
39	Stereotypes of Teenagers' Images in Audiovisual Media Texts about Schools and Universities	A. Fedorov, A. Levitskaya, O. Gorbatkova, A. Mamadaliyev	European Journal of Contemporary Education	Slovakia	X	X	2018, 7(3): 458-464.
40	Inclusion of Techno-Pedagogical Model in Mathematics Teaching-Learning Process	A. García-Santillán, V.S. Molchanova	European Journal of Contemporary Education	Slovakia	X	X	2018, 7(3): 465-484.
41	Public Education System in the Caucasus Region in the 1850s: Unification and Regulation of Educational Process	T.A. Magsumov, S.F. Artemova, O.V. Ustinova, E.V. Vidishcheva	European Journal of Contemporary Education	Slovakia	X	X	2018, 7(3): 598-607.
42	Highland Schools in the Caucasus: Historical Background	O.V. Natolochnaya, N.V. Miku, T.E. Zulfugarzade, A. Médico	European Journal of Contemporary Education	Slovakia	X	X	2018, 7(3): 608-614.
43	Student Clubs in Siberia at the beginning of the XX century (Adapted from Materials of the Journal «Siberian Student»: 1914–1916)	Yu.V. Putilina, V.N. Rodina, O.V. Kirilova, K.V. Taran	European Journal of Contemporary Education	Slovakia	X	X	2018, 7(3): 615-622.
44	Development of Primary Public Education System in Serbia in 1832–1882	G. Rajović, M. Zuev, A.G. Vazerova, M. Trailovic	European Journal of Contemporary Education	Slovakia	X	X	2018, 7(3): 623-629.
45	The Role of Marine Fisheries Research Expeditions of the 18 th –19 th centuries in Establishing Russian Political and Legal Presence in the Arctic	K.S. Zaikov, A.A. Cherkasov, Gao Tianming, N.V. Loukacheva	Bylye Gody	Slovakia	X	X	2018. 50(4): 1456-1470.

46	The Tactics and Strategy of General G.Kh. Zass in the Caucasus	G. Rajović, D.O. Ezhevski, A.G. Vazerova, M. Trailovic	Bylye Gody	Slovakia	X	X	2018. 50(4): 1492-1498.
47	Socio-Economic Situation and Legal Status of Georgian Jews in the XVIII century	N. Ter-Oganov	Bylye Gody	Slovakia	X	X	2018. 50(4): 1507-1517.
48	«Deputative Missions» of the Kazakh Khans, Sultans and Family Governors in the Court of the Russian Emperors in the first half of the 19 th century	Yu.A. Lysenko	Bylye Gody	Slovakia	X	X	2018. 50(4): 1518-1529.
49	The Contribution of Nikolai Vasilievich Varadinov to the Development of Russian Civil Law and Historical and Legal Research	S.I. Degtyarev, V.M. Zavhorodnia, L.G. Polyakova	Bylye Gody	Slovakia	X	X	2018. 50(4): 1530-1537.
50	Sanitary Provision in the Caucasus during the Russian-Persian War of 1826–1828	I.A. Ermachkov, L.A. Koroleva, N.V. Svechnikova, J. Gut	Bylye Gody	Slovakia	X	X	2018. 50(4): 1566-1574.
51	Rion Rowing Flotilla of 1854–1856: Pages of History	V.B. Karataev, S.I. Adinyaev, S.F. Artemova	Bylye Gody	Slovakia	X	X	2018. 50(4): 1625-1631.
52	“Resettlement Fact” – As Seen by the Eyes of Peasants (adapted from Peasants' Letters): Latter half of XIX – early XX centuries	Yu.V. Putilina, V.N. Cherepanova, I.A. Filippova, V.S. Molchanova	Bylye Gody	Slovakia	X	X	2018. 50(4): 1666-1673.
53	On the Ratio of the Linear Forces of the Russian 1 st Pacific and Japanese Squadrons during the Russian-Japanese War of 1904–1905	A.M. Mamadaliyev, A.V. Venkov, N.V. Miku, A. Médico	Bylye Gody	Slovakia	X	X	2018. 50(4): 1734-1743.
54	Evolution of the Institution of the Slave Trade in the Caucasus in the IV–XIX centuries	A.A. Cherkasov, V.G. Ivantsov, M. Šmigel', S.N. Bratanovskii	Bylye Gody	Slovakia	X	X	2018. 50(4): 1334-1346.
55	Among the Mathematics Tasks, Math Courses and Math Exams: How's the Level of Student Anxiety Toward Maths in a Private High School in Mexico?	E. Moreno-García, A. García-Santillán, V.S. Molchanova, E. Plata Campero	European Journal of Contemporary Education	Slovakia	X	X	2018, 7(4): 741-753.

56	The Soft Dimension of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization's Fight Against the "Three Evil Forces". Insights on Counterterrorism Preventive Measures and Youth Education	A. Valleau, K. Rahimov, A. Cherkasov	European Journal of Contemporary Education	Slovakia	X	X	2018, 7(4): 858-873.
57	On the Establishment of the Ruthenian (Ukrainian) University in Austria-Hungary and Its Coverage in "Kievskaya Starina" Journal	S.I. Degyarev, V.M. Zavhorodnia, L.G. Polyakova	European Journal of Contemporary Education	Slovakia	X	X	2018, 7(4): 911-917.
58	Apprenticeship in Secondary Vocational Schools During the Economic Modernization in Late Imperial Russia. Part 1	T.A. Magsumov	European Journal of Contemporary Education	Slovakia	X	X	2018, 7(4): 918-926.
59	Development of the Secondary-Level Education in Serbia from 1808 to the 1870s	G. Rajović, S.N. Bratanovskii, A.G. Vazerova, M. Trailovic	European Journal of Contemporary Education	Slovakia	X	X	2018, 7(4): 927-934.
60	The Abkhazian and Mingrelian Principalities: Historical and Demographic Research	A.A. Cherkasov, L.A. Koroleva, S.N. Bratanovskii, A. Valleau	Vestnik of Saint Petersburg University. History	Russian Federation	X	X	2018, 63(4): 1001-1016.
61	National Units of the Red Army in the Steppe Region and Turkestan During the Civil War	Yu.A. Lysenko	Vestnik of Saint Petersburg University. History	Russian Federation	X	X	2018, 63(4): 1120-1131.
62	Эволюция клятвенных обещаний черкесов в контексте изменения религиозных воззрений в 1800-1855 годах	А.А. Черкасов, Л.А. Королева, С.Н. Братановский, М. Шмигель	Вестник Волгоградского государственного университета. Серия 4: История. Регионоведение. Международные отношения.	Russian Federation	-	X	2018, 23(4): 40-50.
63	К истории одного текста: «положение об управлении донского войска» 1860-х годов	А.Ю. Перетягко	Вестник Волгоградского государственного университета. Серия 4: История. Регионоведение. Международные отношения.	Russian Federation	-	X	2018, 23(2): 100-110.
64	Казачья сословная утопия: замечания хоперских депутатов на проект нового «положения об управлении донским войском» в 1863 г.	А.Ю. Перетягко	Вестник Томского государственного университета. История	Russian Federation	-	X	2018, 55: 33-42.

65	Non-regular troops in the era of decline: a comparative analysis of russian russian and russian grenzers of the 1860s	A.Yu. Peretyatko, T.E. Zulfugarzade	Terra Sebus. Acta Musei Sabesiensis.	Romania	X	-	2018, 10: 225-254.
66	Vocational school and studying youth in the russian revolution of 1905	T.A. Magsumov	Terra Sebus. Acta Musei Sabesiensis.	Romania	X	-	2018, 10: 289-313.
67	The real and alleged problems: on the application of statistical methods for N.A. Maslakovets' s comission	A.Z. Derzhanskaya, A.Y. Peretyatko	Rusin	Moldova	X	X	2018, 54: 107-125.
68	Operating E-Commercial market framework in terms of tourist destination [Funcionamiento del marco de comercio electrónico comercial en términos de destino turístico]	V.S. Molchanova, E. Vidishcheva, I.I. Potapova	Espacios	Venezuela	X	-	2018, 39(34): 7.
69	Pedagogical potential of muslim religious sources in overcoming physical and mental and psychological trials	A.T. Magsumov, R. Sayakhov, V. Yepaneshnikov, I. Nasipov, V. Aitov	Journal of Social Studies Education Research	Turkey	X	-	2018, 9(2): 266-282.
70	Historical-pedagogical research of professional education: Methodology, theory, techniques	T.A. Magsumov, T.M. Aminov, L.Y. Aminova, I.V. Kornilova, A.R. Khasanova, M.K. Akhmetova	Espacios	Venezuela	X	-	2018, 39(35): 14.